

Deliverable 5.3.3.1

EXTENDING A DATA-CENTRIC DISTRIBUTED SIMULATION FRAMEWORK FOR
THE ENERGY DOMAIN

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Extending a Data-Centric Distributed Simulation Framework for the Energy Domain

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General information

Summary

In Task Area 5 of NFDI4Energy, the primary goal is to develop a Simulation-as-a-Service (SimaaS) Hub that offers researchers flexible, interactive, and scalable simulation solutions tailored to the specific demands of energy system research. Within this scope, Measure 5.3 focuses on implementing SimaaS by integrating three simulation middlewares: mosaik, DaceDS, and VILLASframework. To enable seamless interoperability and functionality, each framework requires targeted extensions that enhance their adaptability to the SimaaS ecosystem and meet the requirements of energy researchers.

This paper presents the existing architecture of DaceDS and outlines the planned enhancements to adapt the framework for energy domain applications and seamless integration into SimaaS. Originally developed for the distributed simulation of traffic systems, DaceDS employs a data-centric architecture that facilitates parallel and distributed simulations. The planned improvements aim to extend its capabilities for energy research while addressing scalability, interoperability, and usability.

Key enhancements include integrating containerization technologies to establish a scalable and efficient simulation infrastructure. We add the support of ontologies to enhance interoperability and support the standardization of data and concepts across simulations. Additionally, new scenario-creation functionalities, supported by ontologies and large language models (LLMs), will significantly improve user experience.

To broaden the framework's applicability, domain-specific simulators, such as PyPSA and pandapower, will be integrated, enabling DaceDS to address critical energy research challenges. These extensions not only improve the framework's relevance to energy system research but also provide a robust foundation for incorporating community feedback and driving future development.

Deliverable 5.3.3.1 within NFDI4Energy

Task Area 5 is focused on advancing interdisciplinary simulation efforts in energy system research. Its primary objective is to develop two key services for the NFDI4Energy platform: a software registry and a Simulation-as-a-Service (SimaaS) solution. Within this scope, Measure 5.3 focuses on the conceptualization and implementation of SimaaS, ensuring seamless integration and accessibility for researchers. As part of this effort, the deliverable introduces the newly designed software architecture of DaceDS, a middleware that facilitates distributed simulation. This enhanced architecture will subsequently be integrated into the SimaaS platform, enabling scalable, flexible, and interoperable simulation workflows.

Deliverable description

Introduction

The efficient utilization and continuous advancement of digital tools play a pivotal role in addressing the complex challenges posed by the energy transition. Simulation-as-a-Service (SimaaS) represents an innovative approach to tackling these challenges, particularly in integrating renewable energy sources and analyzing intricate energy systems. By leveraging flexible and scalable platforms, SimaaS allows energy companies and researchers to access advanced simulation tools without significant investments in infrastructure [1]. Furthermore, it fosters enhanced collaboration among stakeholders by enabling the seamless exchange of models and data, thereby supporting the development of innovative solutions for a sustainable energy future [2].

The NFDI4Energy platform seeks to provide researchers with flexible and interactive simulation solutions tailored to the specific needs of energy system research. By incorporating a SimaaS approach, the platform simplifies the execution of co-simulations, enabling the seamless integration of diverse models and simulators [1]. This functionality is critical for addressing the multidisciplinary nature of energy research, where tools must effectively manage the complexity and heterogeneity of energy systems. To advance the capabilities of the NFDI4Energy platform, this work focuses on extending the data-centric distributed simulation framework (DaceDS) [3], initially developed for distributed simulation in the traffic domain. The goal is to adapt DaceDS to the specific requirements of energy system research, facilitating the coupling of diverse energy domain simulators within a federated environment. This extension will not only enable the integration of heterogeneous data and models but also support the exploration of novel research questions. Additionally, we aim to ensure that DaceDS can be efficiently incorporated into the SimaaS architecture of the NFDI4Energy platform, enhancing its utility for researchers and stakeholders alike.

Data-centric Distributed Simulation Framework

DaceDS [1] is a middleware designed for distributed simulations. It enables parallel, co-simulations, and multi-level simulations, improving scalability and interoperability across different simulation environments. DaceDS provides a data-centric approach to coupling distributed simulations. Instead of storing data within individual simulation subcomponents, it utilizes a shared data pool for centralized data management. The framework employs a middleware-based architecture, leveraging Kafka, a topic-based publish/subscribe message streaming system, for efficient communication between components [3]. Components are coupled through the exchange of predefined data tuples using a structured, rule-based procedure. This approach is facilitated by a domain-layer taxonomy that enables structured coupling and flexibility in addressing components [4]. Consequently, DaceDS ensures loose coupling between components, making the system extendable and adaptable for various applications. Additionally, it offers users a graphical interface for composing models or components, triggering scenario simulations, and evaluating simulation results [3].

Although initially developed for the mobility sector, DaceDS is conceptually versatile and can integrate simulators from multiple domains, including traffic and communication.

The architecture of DaceDS is organized into three layers as illustrated in Figure 1.

Each layer has distinct responsibilities:

- **Infrastructure/Core Layer:** This foundational layer defines the mechanisms for data exchange and storage among simulation components. Communication is facilitated by Kafka, and data is stored centrally, accessible to all simulation elements.
- **Coupling Layer:** This intermediate layer specifies the simulator coupling mechanisms. It enables flexible and consistent interaction between components through structured, rule-based procedures that govern the exchange of predefined data tuples.
- **Service/Application Layer:** At the top layer, tools for managing domain and layer definitions are provided, along with capabilities to organize simulation components and resources.

Figure 1: Data-centric Architectural Concept of DaceDS [3]

This three-layer architecture ensures data consistency, flexibility in simulator integration, and intuitive system management and scalability [3].

Planned Extensions

In this chapter, we present the extensions that will be implemented to adapt the framework to the specific requirements of the energy domain and to prepare it for the integration into the SimaaS of the NFDI4Energy platform. The planned extensions include implementing SimaaS capabilities, using Ontologies, improving usability and adding support for new simulators.

Implementing SimaaS capabilities

SimaaS enables users to run simulations flexibly and efficiently in a cloud environment without the need for local installation or administration. Simulations run directly in the cloud and the results are available online. The scalability allows large amounts of data and complex models to be processed, while the flexibility ensures that users can access and customize the services from anywhere with internet access. The technical requirements for SimaaS include a scalable cloud platform that can respond dynamically to changing computing resource needs, as well as lightweight, isolated virtualization through container technologies such as Docker [5].

To facilitate the integration of DaceDS into the architecture of the SimaaS within the NFDI4Energy platform, we will implement containers for the framework. Containers provide an operating system-based virtualization that allows software to be packaged with all its dependencies and executed on different systems [6]. In the SimaaS context, containers are used to provide simulations and scale them flexibly [1]. Container images contain all the necessary files, libraries and configuration files required to run the application. For simulation applications, these images can include the simulation software, runtime environments and configuration files [7].

In summary, container technologies provide a powerful way to efficiently package, deploy and dynamically scale simulation applications. Successful implementation requires the creation of suitable container images and the selection of a suitable runtime environment. Especially in simulation, containers open up new possibilities to optimize the deployment and management of such applications.

Using Ontologies for Message exchange

The energy domain is characterized by a high heterogeneity of the simulators used, making interoperability difficult. An ontology is a formal representation of knowledge about a particular domain that is used to describe concepts, their properties and the relationships between these concepts [8]. Ontologies enable the integration of knowledge from different domains by providing a common terminology and definitions for the terms used in the co-simulation. This helps to avoid ambiguities that can arise

due to different technical languages. In the context of co-simulation, ontologies are used to describe the semantic properties of simulation models and their interfaces [9]. This facilitates the search for suitable models for a specific simulation scenario and the correct coupling of these models.

DaceDS uses domain and layer taxonomies to facilitate the interoperability between the different simulation models. The domain taxonomy formally describes the concepts of a domain, such as the energy domain. The layer taxonomy organizes the concepts within a domain at different abstraction levels, usually represented by different simulators. We enrich the taxonomies with metadata and link them to ontology terms to further standardize them. The components of simulation scenarios, such as models, subsystems or variables, are semantically annotated using the ontology [9]. It includes the assignment of concepts and attributes of the ontology to the corresponding elements of the simulation scenario. This ensures that the meaning of the individual components is clearly defined and that the relationships between the components can be understood. In this way, we create a more consistent and universally valid description.

We plan to integrate the following ontologies into DaceDS:

- Open Energy Ontology [10] for the energy domain.
- Common Core Ontologies [11] for generic concepts.
- SAREF4auto [12] for the transportation domain.
- The International Data Spaces Information Model [13] for the communication domain.

By integrating these ontologies, we reduce the redundancy in the taxonomies and considerably simplify the translation between layers. These steps allow ontologies to be integrated into simulation models and offer great added value for the simulation and co-simulation of complex systems. They not only promote the interoperability and reusability of simulation models, but also the automation of simulation processes. Ontologies are used in various ways in the context of co-simulation to improve the interoperability, planning, execution and analysis of simulations.

Improving Usability

Creating and configuring simulation scenarios remains a complex task, especially when coupling multiple simulators. We are integrating additional tools for model-based scenario creation to support users better in this process. For this, we want to focus primarily on the approaches of Schwarz et al. [14] and Dengler et al. [15]. Schwarz et al. [14] present an approach for an assisted creation process of co-simulation scenarios by using a catalog of simulation models and metadata descriptions of the content to assist the user during the modeling process. They use ontologies to enable co-simulation scenarios to be planned at a higher level of abstraction. This allows domain experts to participate in the modeling without having detailed knowledge of the underlying simulation technologies. Furthermore, ontologies support the automatic generation of co-simulation setups by providing the necessary information for model coupling and execution. Thus, ontologies enable the automatic validation of simulations and the detection of incompatible connections between simulation components.

The description of simulation components and domains using ontologies also offers great potential for using large language models (LLMs). This technology can be used to automate tasks such as creating configuration files or models. Initial approaches by Dengler et al. [15] show how LLMs can generate Python scripts that function as inputs to a simulation environment. The proposed approach uses a multi-level pipeline for the automated generation of simulation scenarios. This involves passing a user description to a Large Language Model (LLM), which generates a Python script. This script is then executed with an implementation of the Python API to generate the required input files for the simulation. A specially fine-tuned conversational model, based on OpenAI's Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT), enables interaction using natural language. This allows users to formulate their simulation scenarios in a simple language, which is translated by the model into executable Python code. To control the model, the LLM receives a preamble that explains the concept of cellular energy systems, introduces relevant

terminology and defines the goal of creating a Python-based description of the given structure. The generated Python script is executed to generate CSV input files that are compatible with i7-AnyEnergy [16], a framework for AnyLogic. These input files serve as the basis for calculating distribution flows and other relevant statistics in the simulation environment.

By implementing new methods for creating simulation scenarios, DaceDS aims to become more accessible for users with different levels of knowledge. Therefore, we are integrating both assisted scenario creation, which is specifically designed towards use by domain experts, and the creation of simulation scenarios using LLMs to enable intuitive use by non-experts as well. The aim of these approaches is to facilitate modeling and improve the efficiency of scenario creation.

Adding support for new Simulators

Finally, we extend DaceDS with wrappers for specific simulators from the energy domain. These include:

PyPSA [17]

PyPSA is a Python-based tool to simulate and optimize modern electrical power systems over multiple time periods [17]. It aims to bridge the gap between power system analysis software and general power system modeling tools. PyPSA provides models for various components, including variable renewables, storage units, coupling with other energy sectors and mixed AC and DC grids. It can model the operation and optimal investment of power systems over multiple time periods and perform both load flow and linearized optimal load flow calculations [17].

pandapower [18]

pandapower is a Python-based tool designed for the automated analysis and optimization of balanced three-phase power grids. It is based on the table structure of the Python library pandas, which makes it particularly user-friendly. Pandapower offers functions such as load flow calculation, optimal load flow calculation, state estimation, short circuit calculation and topological network searches. Pandapower is well suited for the analysis of distribution and transmission systems and has extensive model libraries for electrical components [18].

OpenDSS [19]

OpenDSS is a Delphi-based simulation tool that focuses on the static analysis of power grids, including unbalanced load flow calculations. It is particularly useful for analyzing distribution grids and offers different modes to simulate loads as a function of time [20]. Unlike traditional radial circuit solvers, OpenDSS can easily simulate both meshed and radial distribution systems. It also provides a COM interface for integration with other applications [21].

Simulators with cybersecurity analysis capabilities

As energy systems become increasingly interconnected and digitalized, including the integration of renewables, distributed energy sources and IoT-based communications, cybersecurity is becoming a key research topic [22]. Simulations of cybersecurity in smart grids enable an in-depth investigation of the complex interactions between power grids and communication systems as well as a detailed analysis of the impact of cyberattacks on grid stability and security [23]. Simulations can be used to identify potential security gaps and vulnerabilities in smart grids, which can proactively prevent critical infrastructure collapses and economic losses [24]. Simulations also offer the opportunity to test the effectiveness of various security measures and counter-strategies against cyber attacks [24]. Another advantage of simulation is its cost-effectiveness, as it does not require any physical infrastructure and has no impact on real operations, unlike real field tests or hardware-in-the-loop simulations [25]. Important aspects in the simulation of cyberattacks include the consideration of realistic attack scenarios based on known threats and vulnerabilities, the inclusion of communication delays between the components of the smart grid and the quantification of the effects of cyberattacks on the smart grid, for example in terms of grid stability, power supply security and economic losses [22]. Simulations of cyber security in smart grids offer a valuable opportunity to identify potential vulnerabilities at an early stage and to test the effectiveness of security measures. They are an essential tool for ensuring the security and resilience of smart grids in an increasingly digitalized and connected world. For this reason, we would also like to integrate simulations of cyber security in smart grids into DaceDS.

These planned enhancements aim to improve the functionality and usability of DaceDS and establish it as a component for the energy domain within NFDI4Energy.

Conclusion

The planned extensions to the DaceDS framework represent an important step towards meeting the specific requirements of the energy domain and enabling seamless integration into the NFDI4Energy platform’s SimaaS. Therefore, we expand DaceDS in several areas as shown in figure 2:

- Integration of containers for efficient and scalable simulations.
- Extension of the coupling layer through the use of ontologies.
- Improvement of the Service/Application Layer with new features for scenario creation.
- Integration of additional simulators from the energy domain.

Figure 2: Extended Architectural Concept of DaceDS

By integrating containers, we create an efficient and scalable infrastructure for simulations. Using ontologies to enrich the domain and layer taxonomies increases interoperability and facilitates the standardization of concepts and data. In addition, we improve usability through new scenario-creation features that utilize ontologies and support from LLMs. By integrating specific simulators from the energy domain, such as PyPSA or pandapower, we are expanding the range of applications of DaceDS and addressing key requirements in research and practice. The planned extensions offer potential for improving research processes and provide a valuable basis for integrating feedback from the community and further developing the framework’s functionalities in a targeted manner.

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